

Integrating DevOps with Problem-Based Learning: Transforming Project Management Education in Computer Science Curricula

Cristiano Jesus^{1,2,3}, Francisco Claro¹, Ivan Amorim¹, Paulo C. Anacleto Filho³, Lúcio Garcia Veraldo Júnior⁴, Sérgio Ivan Lopes^{1,2,5}

¹CiTin – Centro de Interface Tecnológico Industrial, 4970-786, Arcos de Valdevez, Portugal

²ADiT-Lab, Instituto Politécnico de Viana Do Castelo, Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial Nun'Álvares, 4900-347, Viana Do Castelo, Portugal

³ALGORITMI Research Center/LASI, University of Minho, 4710-057, Guimarães, Portugal

⁴UNIFESP – Universidade Federal de São Paulo

⁵IT – Instituto de Telecomunicações, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193, Aveiro, Portugal

Email: cristiano.jesus@citin.pt, francisco.claro@citin.pt, ivan.amorim@citin.pt, pauloanacletof@gmail.com,
lucio.veraldo@infinityacademy3d.com.br, sil@estg.ipvc.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874390>

Abstract

This article explores a materialist approach to education, emphasising tangible structures – tools, technologies, and organizational frameworks – in shaping learning rather than focusing on symbolic representations or pre-existing knowledge. We illustrate this by applying DevOps principles in a Project Management course. DevOps, an approach rooted in the material realities of the tech industry (efficiency, collaboration, continuous delivery), integrates development and operations through automation and shared practices. Our teaching-learning experience embedded project planning within the DevOps workflow, using constant feedback and practical, problem-solving projects. Student teams developed, deployed, and monitored systems, reflecting on theoretical foundations during DevOps ceremonies. The final student pitches highlighted the impact of this experience on their academic and professional growth.

Keywords: Problem Based Learning; Active Learning; Project Management; DevOps; Scientific Materialism

1 Introduction

The materialist tradition is interested in observing and analyzing the behavior of structures, whether physical or organizational, and how they are used as resources, rather than focusing on what they mean or how they are represented symbolically. In education, this translates into an emphasis on tools, technologies, architecture and organizational structure, processes and concrete practices that reflect the material conditions of the target agents. In this approach, instead of starting from baselines or knowledge bases as an education strategy, we start from a structure that enables, or even conditions, actions, decisions and practices that are expected and defended by the reference models.

Project Management constitutes a competency that transcends a single scientific domain. Its versatile nature characterizes it, and it applies to virtually all sectors of the economy and the production of goods and services. Due to this broad applicability, its tools and procedures originate from various fields, such as Software Engineering, Civil Engineering, Industry, multiple areas of Communication (including Journalism and Marketing), Health, Education, the Public Sector, the Financial Sector, Commerce, in addition to the core specialties of Business Sciences, such as Management, Accounting, Human Resources, among others.

Thus, Project Management does not rely on static models for problem-solving but rather on a body of scientific and professional knowledge that serves as a reference guide and baseline. As a result, this guide is not applied

literally in any specific case since such conduct would represent an orthodox rigor that is disproportionate and unsuitable to the reality of each project.

This inherent characteristic of Project Management poses a particular challenge to its teaching, as it is essentially a practice-oriented discipline. Therefore, teaching and learning strategies based exclusively on the exhaustive study of concepts, techniques, and models have proven ineffective, tiresome, and demotivating. On the other hand, Project Management does not constitute an unqualified practice in which improvisation is acceptable.

DevOps is an approach that integrates software development (Dev) and technology infrastructure operations (Ops) through tools, automation and collaborative practices. It directly reflects the material conditions of the technology industry, where efficiency, collaboration and continuous delivery are essential, as well as a culture geared towards these values. DevOps is not just about tools and procedures, but about how, integrated into a process, they promote teamwork, efficient communication and continuous improvement, essential skills for any engineer.

This article presents a successful case of teaching-learning experience in Project Management in which planning was treated as one of the functions in the DevOps workflow, seamlessly integrated with the other functions through permanent and transparent feedback. Through practical, problem-solving-oriented projects, student teams adopted and applied procedures reflecting the essential theoretical foundations to develop, deploy and monitor systems. Reflections on these fundamentals were discussed during the planning cycle ceremonies, in sprint review and sprint retrospective meetings. At the end, the students presented pitches in which they expressed the results of this experience on their academic and professional journey.

The case presented in this article was developed in the third year of the Computer Networks and Systems Engineering program at the Polytechnic Institute of Viana do Castelo. Based on philosophical assumptions of materialist orientation, the initial hypothesis (Hypothesis 1) was that a material production structure is a prerequisite for implementing theoretical-practical educational activities in the Project Management discipline. For this purpose, a DevOps platform was selected as the most suitable framework (Hypothesis 2), considering that future professionals trained in this program will presumably work in multifunctional teams dedicated to technological development, involving software and computational systems, and will, in principle, be responsible for infrastructure—a scenario for which the DevOps philosophy is fully aligned. The experience was a success, as will be demonstrated in the quantitative and qualitative evaluation of this case.

2 Theoretical Framing

Among the various approaches in the discussion about the appropriation of knowledge, at its most fundamental bases in ontology and epistemology, the materialist worldview presupposes the existence of a primary reality, called material, which can be observed and verified. In terms of scientific production, logical positivism, atomism, determinism, and objectivism are the central philosophical principles of this view, providing guidelines and methodological tools for the production of scientific knowledge, essentially based on physical reality and experience, within the limits of intellectual analysis, categorization, and conceptualization. Determinism assumes that events are predetermined by the conditions in which they occur, so that they can be predicted and controlled through consciousness and scientific reason (Águila, 2024).

From this perspective, new materialism overcomes the radical duality between matter and observer. It gives way to the vision of reality as an interconnected network in which action is distributed among human and non-human actors, so that reality is considered to be shaped by interactions that substantially challenge conventional notions of causality, evolving from a one-way process to a mutual and reciprocal process in which

entities are both cause and effect of the relationships between them. This position also changes epistemic authority, that is, who determines the validity of knowledge. Material objects do not function as arbiters of scientific claims; instead, in place of absolute correspondence between actions and concept, what matters is what can be observed in the interaction between the social and material aspects of scientific claims, in the result of the dance of resistance and accommodation between material objects and subjects (Tang & Cooper, 2025).

Aligned with this idea, now more specifically regarding technology, based on philosophers who thought about technology such as Martin Heidegger, Jacques Ellul, and Lewis Mumford, Achterhuis (2001b) states that technology should not be thought of as applied natural science, but rather as a “system,” because it is more a way of life than an instrument. In the view of these philosophers, the traditional, and so to speak, naive, view of technology assumes that it is simply the practical application of scientific discoveries. Still, it has its logic, independent of science. Technology shapes science as much as it is shaped by it, because it reorganizes human existence and redefines our way of being in the world. Thus, modern technology is not a helpful tool, but rather a mode of existence, an interdependent network where techniques, institutions, and values mutually reinforce each other, obeying a systemic logic and establishing power relations, because they are intrinsically integrated into social systems, therefore, it is not controllable by individuals, and cannot be assimilated as knowledge in a totalizing way (Tijmes, 2001).

This conceptual and epistemic evolution challenges the understanding of engineering, the role of the engineer, and consequently, the training of engineers, that is, engineering education. Gunay (2018) states that engineering is the practical and creative application of scientific principles to design, develop, and build structures, machines, equipment, manufacturing processes, and specific functions economically and safely. It uses science, mathematics, and design, essentially a problem-solving activity. The engineer transforms ideas into projects and, through technology, into physical products, acting simultaneously in the virtual world (ideas and scientific principles), in the intangible world (projects), and in the tangible world (real products) (Bulleit et al., 2014; Gabbay et al., 2009).

However, as we have seen, interventions in these worlds are not simply mechanical. Therefore, they are mediated relationships. Especially in the training of engineers, one particular challenge must be noted, which concerns the evolution of the nature of the product delivered by engineers (Bulleit et al., 2014). According to Tijmes (2001), modern technology differs from traditional technology because it aims to produce devices, instead of things. Devices are technological means without context, while things are socially embedded. For example, a faucet is a device, and a well is a thing. Unlike the faucet, the well requires familiarity with its machinery and operating conditions. Human involvement and interaction with reality are greater in handling the well than with the faucet. Therefore, modern technology is modeled based on a specific pattern that consists of a device that separates ends and means. The means form the hidden machinery, configured to produce the end safely, easily, instantly, and ubiquitously (Davis, 1998).

Therefore, to think about engineering and the training of engineers, it is necessary to consider the process of instrumentalization, which according to Achterhuis (2001a), is how a technical artifact becomes a usable instrument in society. According to the author, this involves forms of objectification and subjectification associated with a functional relationship with the world and consists of two levels. On the first level, four moments of technical practice occur: (1) Decontextualization, in which the natural objects are removed from their original contexts (e.g., extracting a tree from a forest for carpentry); (2) reductionism, in which decontextualized things are reduced to aspects that can be integrated into a technical network; (3) autonomization, in which the technical actor operates in isolation, minimizing environmental feedback (e.g., consumers in supermarkets lacking knowledge of production processes); and (4) positioning, in which Humans

are categorized functionally, either as labor or consumers. At this level, modern technology organizes the world into a structured, calculable system where elements are primed for technical manipulation. On the second level, it also includes four moments: (1) Systematization, in which technical objects are coordinated into systems and reintroduced into environments; (2) mediation, in which the aesthetic and ethical considerations are embedded into technical objects; (3) vocation, in which work environments are designed to align with workers' professional and personal engagement; finally (4) initiative, in which users adapt technical systems through creative or innovative applications..

Another way of looking at this process of the relationship between human beings, technology, and the world is through their mediators, and in what matters to engineering and engineering education, through the act of appropriating this process, which in theory, is what is supposedly expected of the engineering professional. According to Verbeek (2001), each of the stages of mediation and appropriation marks a specific form of experience and intervention, namely, (1) unmediated perception, in which the subject interacts directly with the world, resulting in immediate, empirical experience that is not shaped by instruments or concepts; (2) mediated perception, which technology acts as an intermediary, enabling the subject to pursue specific goals and transforming the relationship with the world into an instrumental one; (3) incorporation relations, in which technology becomes an extension of the subject, forming a hybrid agent that expands the subject's capacity for action and perception (e.g., using glasses); (4) hermeneutic relations, which the subject adopts an interpretive stance, where technology not only mediates but also reveals or translates aspects of the world (e.g., maps or scientific instruments); (5) alterity relations, in which technology is recognized as an autonomous agent capable of interacting with and altering the world in ways beyond the subject's direct control; finally (6), background relations, in which technology becomes integrated and almost invisible in daily life, forming a backdrop for human activity (e.g., automatic heating systems), so that the environment is experienced as a technologically mediated whole rather than through explicit manipulation of devices.

Therefore, materialist orientations converge toward the view of technology and engineering products as forms belonging to social organization, so the realization and maintenance of concrete social structures consonant with objective reality and rooted in our interaction with materiality is a prevailing factor for our development as human beings and professionals. Our connection with material things in the physical world fundamentally defines our understanding of nature and our relationship with it. As such, materiality cannot be marginalized in education and professional training to privilege the role of pure thought and knowledge at the secondary level of the language structure. In education, both material structures and the worldliness of the individual are starting points for the evolution of consciousness (Korte et al., 2022; Tang & Cooper, 2025).

2.1 Problem-Solving Approach

Constructivism, grounded in the works of Piaget, Vygotsky, and Dewey, is a theory of knowledge and an educational approach that understands learning as occurring through the active construction of knowledge by the student, based on experiences and social interactions. The teacher's role is to mediate and create environments that foster investigation, experimentation, and reflection, making the student the protagonist of the learning process (Evendi & Verawati, 2021; Zaccaria et al., 2025). Therefore, student-centered approaches, active learning, integration of technologies, development of socio-emotional, cognitive, and non-cognitive skills (Rulida et al., 2024), and the importance of collaborative and reflective environments are fundamental for shaping engineers who can act consciously and critically in the modern world, where technology is intrinsically and transparently embedded in reality (Akolekar et al., 2025; Domínguez-Valerio et al., 2025; Gujarati et al., 2025). These trends aim to prepare students for complex challenges by promoting autonomy, creativity, critical thinking, and the ability to solve problems in real-world contexts (Epstein et al., 1996; Kilmann & Thomas, 1977).

Active methodologies originated in health courses, especially in medicine. Still, today they are widely used in STEAM education, an approach that integrates the areas of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (El Fathi et al., 2025). These methodologies provide interdisciplinary, collaborative learning based on practical projects, encouraging students to solve real and complex problems by combining knowledge from these fields (Cline & Powers, 1998; López-Silva et al., 2025; Ramos-Mejía & Padilla, 2025). Several active methodologies that emphasize problem-solving through relationships with the environment and with people are widely recognized by the scientific community, including (Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Kizhukarakkatu, 2025; Naveh et al., 2022; Wood, 2003):

- Problem-Based Learning (PBL): Focused on the collaborative resolution of authentic and open-ended problems, promoting autonomy, critical thinking, knowledge retention, and social skills;
- Project-Based Learning (PrBL): Long-term interdisciplinary projects in which students explore complex topics, connecting theory and practice in real-world contexts;
- Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL): Learning based on investigation, where the emphasis is on the process of discovery and experimentation guided by essential questions;
- Design Thinking: A creative and iterative process for solving complex problems, stimulating innovation, creativity, and critical thinking;
- Experiential Learning: Learning through direct experience, valuing reflection on practice;
- Collaborative Learning: Working in small groups, promoting positive interdependence, individual responsibility, and the development of social and cognitive skills;
- Argumentation: Development of informal reasoning and discourse skills, which are fundamental for building scientific knowledge;
- Multiple Intelligences: Considering different learning styles and valuing skills beyond traditional verbal and mathematical abilities.

The above mentioned methodologies should not be applied as simple laboratory exercises with predictable paths and previously calculated outcomes (Maheshwari et al., 2025). In light of reflections on scientific materialism, it is essential to consider that these methodologies must be guided by principles that promote structured freedom based on concrete foundations, strategically constructed and oriented toward specific goals by experienced teachers (E. Crawley et al., 2014; E. F. Crawley et al., 2014; Laursen & Ryberg, 2025). In this way, they foster the progressive construction of knowledge through problem-solving and challenges based on scientific and professional frameworks, also promoting student engagement, since active involvement, curiosity, and motivation are essential dimensions for strengthening this commitment, a fundamental element for learning (Canavan, 2008; Tjiparuro, 2025; Zhao, 2025).

2.2 DevOps and Project Management in the Context of Software Development and Computational Systems

DevOps emerged to eliminate barriers between development and operations, promoting collaboration, automation, and continuous integration to accelerate delivery and increase system reliability (Chen & Suo, 2023). DevSecOps expands this scope by integrating security practices from the beginning of the software lifecycle (Akbar et al., 2025). The DevOps approach is based on the pillars of Culture, Automation, Measurement, and Sharing (CAMS) (Srajan et al., 2024); therefore, it is seen both as a set of agile practices and as a cultural movement, fostering collaboration among teams, process automation, and continuous value delivery (Wiedemann et al., 2023). Thus, DevOps functions as an engineering platform encompassing infrastructure, processes, relationships, and values, serving as a complete ecosystem for project management (Al-Nakeeb et al., 2024). In this context, the engineer responsible for project management finds an efficient structure, which

incorporates even elements of the Theory of Restrictions (ToC) (Kendrick, 2023), for integrating teams, managing human resources, communication, scope, schedule, risks, quality, and costs, with specific guidelines and tools for each knowledge area to ensure both horizontal and vertical integration across all of them (Akbar et al., 2024; El Khatib et al., 2024).

Agile methodologies are revitalized within DevOps (Beard et al., 2024). Their fundamental principles— iterative development, continuous feedback, and cross-functional collaboration—enable ongoing transformation and adaptation (Kopare et al., 2025). Instead of requiring constant buy-in, self-monitoring, and motivation from Scrum Masters, these principles become structurally embedded in the relationships among the various stakeholders involved (Sravan et al., 2024). With DevOps, transparency, open communication, and collective problem-solving are not just rules to be followed, but rather the active and inevitable dynamic of these relationships. The evolution of agile management and automation tools keeps pace with the need for rapid adaptation, process integration, and data-driven decision support, fitting comfortably within the dynamic nature of projects and facilitating workflow integration, collaboration, and real-time monitoring (Wiedemann et al., 2023). Implementing DevOps and agile methodologies transforms technical processes and organisational culture, promoting empathy, cooperation, real-time communication, and a focus on continuous improvement. Using digital platforms and automation, enhanced by DevOps, facilitates the integration of business areas, processes, and technology while reducing costs (El Khatib et al., 2024).

Therefore, DevOps has the potential to be an essential ally in the transition from traditional educational environments to agile practices, as it is a controlled ecosystem with broad possibilities for technological and relational exploration, as well as offering opportunities for the development of multifunctional (T-shaped) skills and exposing students to practical and iterative scenarios, preparing them for dynamic work environments (Beard et al., 2024).

DevOps is not only a material and technological platform for integrating and running software applications; it also structures the entire process of planning, developing, and deploying software. This structuring significantly defines the standards adopted and disciplines the collaboration among the various stakeholders involved. As an educational strategy for project management instruction, DevOps serves as a controlled microcosm for applying concepts and fostering collaborative relationships. This objective aligns with both materialist and constructivist approaches to education, as it enables experiential learning and the development of practical skills in a real-world, iterative environment.

3 Learning Methodologies, Strategies and Assessment Methods

The Project Management course, an integral part of the Computer Networks and Systems Engineering program at the Polytechnic Institute of Viana do Castelo, is taught in the third year of the students' academic path. The program aims to train professionals with competencies in Computer Programming, Applications and Services, Network and Communications Engineering, Systems Engineering, Systems and Network Administration, Network Design, Project Management, and Consulting in Networks, Systems, and Security. The graduate profile is predominantly oriented towards information technology infrastructure, encompassing software and computer systems programming skills.

The Project Management course unit aims to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for effective involvement in the planning, execution, monitoring, and evaluation phases of software projects in various organizational contexts. At the same time, it seeks to raise students' awareness of the theoretical frameworks of Project Management and the application of agile methodologies.

The case presented in this article was developed during the first semester of the 2024/2025 academic year, corresponding to the period between September 2024 and February 2025. As active learning strategies, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) methodologies were employed, supported by collaborative learning techniques and oriented towards developing multiple intelligences. These strategies were aligned with interpersonal skills and soft skills essential to project management, as established in the Individual Competence Baseline for Project, Program, and Portfolio Management of the International Project Management Association (IPMA). Among these competencies are: self-reflection and personal management, integrity and reliability, interpersonal communication, relationship and commitment, leadership, teamwork, conflict and crisis management, resourcefulness, and negotiation.

Before addressing the technical content of Project Management, students were introduced to the fundamental concepts of DevOps, including its structure, objectives, involved technologies, and the production systems it targets, covering topics such as enterprise architecture, software architecture, methodologies, procedures, and tools.

The challenge proposed to students consisted of implementing an on-premises DevOps platform for a software development laboratory within a non-profit Technology and Innovation Center, primarily funded by publicly financed projects aimed at innovation and technology transfer. A particularly critical aspect of this scenario is the highly volatile nature of the services provided, which are always linked to time-bound funded projects.

The 38 students were introduced to essential concepts and encouraged to deepen their understanding using the visual tool Process Model Canvas (PM Canvas), applying concepts such as SMART Objectives, scope, requirements, Work Breakdown Structure, risks, costs, and more. They organized themselves into nine teams, self-assigning roles such as Project Manager, Scrum Master, Product Owner, and Developers. They also developed a stakeholder management plan based on a RACI matrix (responsible, accountable, consulted, and informed). These initial actions resulted in the creation of the Project Charter document.

In response to the specific challenge of the fictional scenario, especially regarding the critical aspects of funding sources and the mission of technology transfer, students were prompted to develop a rationale for the acceptance criteria of the technological tools to be adopted for the DevOps platform. They concluded that the tools should meet the following requirements:

- The tool must be open source, given the organization's mission of technology transfer;
- The tool must be a community edition, as it should constitute an on-premises platform, and the team should foster a sense of collaboration for innovation and technological advancement;
- The tool must have a self-hosted option, since cloud versions may be adopted if there are ongoing funded projects with a budget for this purpose. However, upon their conclusion, all results must be reproducible on the organization's infrastructure.

Based on these criteria, the teams conducted extensive research, the results of which are concisely presented in Table 1.

Students were provided with tutorials and technical guides for installing and integrating all tools within a DevOps platform based on Kubernetes or Kubernetes distributions such as Microk8s, K3d, Minikube, and Kind.

Table 1: Tools according to acceptance criteria

Tool	Open Source*	Self-Hosted*	Community Edition*	Eligible*
Openproject	Y	Y	Y	Y
Trello	N	N	N	N
Clickup	N	N	N	N
Taiga	Y	Y	Y	Y
GitHub	N	N	N	N
GitLab	Y	Y	Y	Y
Jenkins	Y	Y	Y	Y
Sonarqube	Y	Y	Y	Y
AWX & Ansible	Y	Y	Y	Y
ArgoCD	Y	Y	Y	Y
Prometheus	Y	Y	Y	Y
Grafana	Y	Y	Y	Y
Google Drive	N	N	N	N
Nextcloud	Y	Y	Y	Y
Google Docs	N	N	N	N
Collabora	Y	Y	Y	Y

*Yes (Y), No (N)

Given the context of resource management and the constraint of having no financial budget for the course, students were challenged to identify alternative solutions for provisioning the platform. They researched a range of options, from widely known providers such as AWS, Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, Oracle Cloud, and IBM Cloud, to other platforms offering limited but suitable free resources for educational purposes, such as Oracle Cloud Free Tier, KodeKloud Hands-On Labs, and iximiuz Labs. Some teams chose to create clusters using their equipment. In contrast, with voluntary support from an Industrial Designer and through self-funding, one team developed a cluster using Raspberry Pi devices and 3d printing, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Raspberry Pi Cluster

The cluster setup includes four Raspberry Pi 5 devices, each with 4GB of RAM, memory cards, and heat sinks, as well as an industrial power supply. With the addition of a 3D-printed case made from PLA filament, the total investment amounted to 351.83€. With this configuration, high availability and load balancing cannot be guaranteed. These limitations sparked discussions among the students, prompting them to explore and better understand the concepts and requirements necessary to implement such features.

The students transformed the challenge into projects by creating epics, user stories, tasks, and kanbans. They developed sprint strategies and conducted sprint review meetings, sprint retrospectives, and backlog refinement sessions, with the teacher assuming the role of the client. The projects were presented in two stages. The intermediate presentation served to correct approaches and prepare for the final presentation.

For the individual component, students created a five-minute video pitch in which they reflected on their experiences, describing the barriers they encountered and the value they identified in the course and its format. Assessment was based on students' progress in teamwork, approach to technical challenges, commitment, and individual development.

The course had 38 students enrolled. Six students neither attended classes nor participated in any activities. Two students chose not to complete the assigned activities and instead took the exams, achieving the minimum passing grade. Among the students who actively participated, only three received the minimum passing grade because they did not submit the pitch video assignment; the rest scored between 15 and 18 out of a maximum of 20. As a result, the overall pass rate was 84.2%.

4 Conclusion

A general sense of satisfaction could be observed through the video pitches produced by the students. Most students had never heard of the DevOps philosophy, and their previous understanding of project management was limited to a simple to-do list.

Given the challenging task of implementing a complex platform such as DevOps, all teams sought external assistance from individuals with experience in the field. This engagement significantly contributed to raising students' awareness and motivation, as they realized firsthand that DevOps is a highly sought-after and relatively scarce skill in the job market, which could serve as a distinguishing factor for them.

However, some constraints were identified. One student, who demonstrated clear leadership qualities and thus was influential among peers, was initially critical and resistant to the course format, expressing a preference for a traditional, lecture-based approach. This student did not initially see the value in a platform requiring the integration of many tools and felt that project management was not adequately addressed in a course dedicated to this subject. Nevertheless, as the project progressed and the initial installation and configuration phases were completed, the student understood and embraced the proposed strategy. In their pitch, the student acknowledged the value of all the competencies developed.

Another challenge was related to the formal structure of the course and institutional regulations. Some students chose to take exams and resit assessments after the regular assessment period, thereby opting out of the proposed project-based evaluations. For these students, it was necessary to develop traditional tests, and their evaluation was based on the core content of project management as an area of knowledge.

Acknowledgments

This work received funding from the investment "DRIVOLUTION – Transição para a fábrica do futuro", with reference 02/C05-i01.02/2022.PC644913740-00000022, and has been partially funded by investment "Missão Interface", with reference 03/C05-i02/2022.P10, both under the Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan. P.C.A.F. is supported by FCT—Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UID/00319/Centro ALGORITMI (ALGORITMI/UM). P.C.A.F. gratefully acknowledges FCT's support through his PhD grant number 2023.00456.BDANA

Disclosure of Interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

- Achterhuis, H. (2001a). Andrew Feenberg: Farewell to Dystopia. In A. W. M. Meijers, *The Empirical Turn in the Philosophy of Technology* (Illustrated edition). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Achterhuis, H. (2001b). Introduction: American Philosophers of Technology. In A. W. M. Meijers, *The Empirical Turn in the Philosophy of Technology* (Illustrated edition). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Águila, C. (2024). Del materialismo al transmateralismo en educación física: Hacia una pedagogía de la corporeidad consciente. *Revista Complutense de Educación*, 35(3), 565–573. <https://doi.org/10.5209/rced.85980>

- Akbar, M. A., Khan, A. A., Islam, N., & Mahmood, S. (2024). DevOps project management success factors: A decision-making framework. *Software - Practice and Experience*, 54(2), 257–280. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3269>
- Akbar, M. A., Khan, A. A., Mahmood, S., & Hyrynsalmi, S. (2025). Management of DevSecOps Process: An Empirical Investigation. *Software - Practice and Experience*. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3419>
- Akolekar, H., Jhamnani, P., Kumar, V., Tailor, V., Pote, A., Meena, A., Kumar, K., Challa, J. S., & Kumar, D. (2025). The role of generative AI tools in shaping mechanical engineering education from an undergraduate perspective. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-93871-z>
- Al-Nakeeb, A., Khatib, M. E., AlHarmoodi, S., Salami, M., Al Shehhi, H., Al Naqbi, A., Al Nuaimi, M., & Alzoubi, H. M. (2024). Digital Transformation and Disruptive Technologies: Effect of Cloud Computing and Devops on Managing Projects. *Studies in Big Data*, 147, 39–62. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-55221-2_3
- Beard, J. W., Storey, V. C., Samuel, B., Lukyanenko, R., Wiedemann, A., Schuff, D., Ogunseye, S., Islamzada, Z., & Islamzada, F. (2024). *Agile Development: The Promise, the Reality, the Opportunity*. 3690, 7–17. Scopus.
- Bulleit, W., Schmidt, J., Alvi, I., Nelson, E., & Rodriguez-Nikl, T. (2014). Philosophy of Engineering: What It Is and Why It Matters. *Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice*, 141, 02514003. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EI.1943-5541.0000205](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EI.1943-5541.0000205)
- Canavan, B. (2008). A summary of the findings from an evaluation of problem-based learning carried out at three UK universities. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Education*, 45(2), 175–180. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.7227/IJEEE.45.2.9>
- Chen, T., & Suo, H. (2023). Architecture Design of Enterprise Information System Based on Docker and DevOps Technology. *2023 7th International Conference on Management Engineering, Software Engineering and Service Sciences (ICMSS)*, 19–23. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMSS56787.2023.10117715>
- Cline, M. J., & Powers, G. J. (1998). *Problem based learning in a chemical engineering undergraduate laboratory*. ASEE Annual Conference Proceedings. Scopus.
- Crawley, E. F., Malmqvist, J., Östlund, S., Brodeur, D. R., & Edström, K. (2014). *Rethinking engineering education: The CDIO approach, second edition* (p. 311). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05561-9>
- Crawley, E., Malmqvist, J., Östlund, S., & Brodeur, D. (2014). *Adapting and Implementing a CDIO Approach* (pp. 181–207). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05561-9_8
- Davis, M. (1998). Thinking Like an Engineer: Studies in the Ethics of a Profession. *Online Ethics Center*. <https://doi.org/10.18130/a7st-6959>
- Domínguez-Valerio, C. M., Moral-Cuadra, S., Lendínez Turón, A., & Orgaz-Agüera, F. (2025). Problem-based learning for the development of sustainable attitudes and knowledge in engineering students: Evidence from the Dominican Republic. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-11-2023-0564>
- El Fathi, T., Saad, A., Larhzil, H., Lamri, D., & Al Ibrahim, E. M. (2025). Integrating generative AI into STEM education: Enhancing conceptual understanding, addressing misconceptions, and assessing student acceptance. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 7(1). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43031-025-00125-z>
- El Khatib, M., Salami, M., Shehhi, H., Naqbi, A., & Nuaimi, M. (2024). How Cloud Computing and DevOps Can Add value to Managing Projects. *International Journal of Theory of Organization and Practice (IJTOP)*, 3, 156–176. <https://doi.org/10.54489/ijtop.v3i2.312>
- Epstein, S., Pacini, R., Denes-Raj, V., & Heier, H. (1996). Individual Differences in Intuitive–Experiential and Analytical–Rational Thinking Styles. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71, 390–405. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.71.2.390>
- Evendi, E., & Verawati, N. (2021). Evaluation of Student Learning Outcomes in Problem-Based Learning: Study of Its Implementation and Reflection of Successful Factors. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 7, 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v7iSpecialIssue.1099>
- Gabbay, D. M., Thagard, P., & Woods, J. (2009). *Philosophy of Technology and Engineering Sciences* (A. W. M. Meijers, Ed.; First Edition). North Holland.
- Gujarati, A. M., Bhatt, M. J., Joshi, H. B., & Vasantha, S. V. (2025). Exploring the impact of problem-based learning and traditional lecture delivery: A comparative case study. In *Digital Transformation and Sustainability of Business* (pp. 500–504). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003606185-118>
- Gunay, D. (2018). *The Philosophy of Technology and Engineering*. 1. <https://doi.org/10.26701/uad.371662>
- Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2004). Problem-based learning: What and how do students learn? *Educational Psychology Review*, 16(3), 235–266. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:EDPR.0000034022.16470.f3>
- Kendrick, C. (2023). Implementing value: Evaluating systems frameworks and their impact on scalable systems implementations. *Issues in Information Systems*, 24(1), 245–259. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.48009/1_iis_2023_121
- Kilmann, R. H., & Thomas, K. W. (1977). Developing a forced-choice measure of conflict-handling behavior: The “Mode” Instrument. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 37(2), 309–325. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447703700204>
- Kizhukarakkattu, J. A. (2025). Pedagogical approaches in STEAM education: Fostering innovation and creativity in the classroom. In *Transformative Approaches to STEAM Integration in Modern Education* (pp. 79–101). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-7408-5.ch004>
- Kopare, A., Jebaraj, N. R. S., Shrivastava, V. K., & Dongre, D. (2025). Agile management: Adapting IT strategies to rapidly changing technologies. In *Tech-Driven Strategies: Leveraging Information Technology in Business Management* (pp. 91–116). Scopus.
- Korte, R., Phd, M., Frezza, S., & Nordquest, D. (2022). Philosophy and Engineering Education: Practical Ways of Knowing. *Synthesis Lectures on Engineering, Science, and Technology*, 4, 1–76. <https://doi.org/10.2200/S01161ED1V01Y202201EST020>
- Laursen, L. N., & Ryberg, T. (2025). Digitalisation of engineering design education: Structured freedom, flipped engagement, hybridity, and transparency. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 50(1), 194–213. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2024.2331257>
- López-Silva, M., Carmenates-Hernández, D., Requejo-Pacheco, G., Brown-Manrique, O., Mujica-Cervantes, A., Brazao-Tembe, F., & Guivala, B. (2025). Flipped classroom and problem-based learning in teaching hydrology to civil engineering students in Cuba, Peru and Mozambique. *Tecnología y Ciencias Del Agua*, 16(2), 295–326. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.24850/j-tyca-2025-02-07>
- Maheshwari, S., Rajendran, R., & Iyer, S. (2025). Mapping Challenges in Teaching-Learning Software Testing: Limitations and Unaddressed Issues in Contemporary Research. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 2400 CCIS, 181–191. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-84391-4_15

- Michelfelder, D. P., McCarthy, N., & Goldberg, D. E. (Eds.). (2013). *Philosophy and Engineering: Reflections on Practice, Principles and Process* (Vol. 15). Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7762-0>
- Naveh, G., Bakun-Mazor, D., Tavor, D., & Shelef, A. (2022). Problem-based Learning in A Theoretical Course in Civil Engineering: Students' Perspectives. *Advances in Engineering Education*, 10(3), 46–67. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.18260/3-1-1153-36033>
- Ramos-Mejía, A., & Padilla, K. (2025). A Problem-Based Learning Electrochemistry Course for Undergraduate Students to Develop Complex Thinking. *Education Sciences*, 15(3). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15030320>
- Rulida, D., Cano, J., & Andrin, G. (2024). Non-Cognitive Skills as Correlates to Academic Performance Among Senior High School Students. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, 7, 222–249. <https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijms-v7i1p131>
- Sravan, N. K., Vuyyuru, V. A., Gottapu, P., Theeda, A., & Peddineni, L. (2024). Agile Management Tools: Technological Evaluations and Future Archetype. *2024 4th International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Social Networking (ICPCSN)*, 914–918. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPCSN62568.2024.00154>
- Tang, K.-S., & Cooper, G. (2025). The Role of Materiality in an Era of Generative Artificial Intelligence. *Science & Education*, 34(2), 731–746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-024-00508-0>
- Tijmes, P. (2001). Albert Borgman: Technology and the Character of Everyday Life. In A. W. M. Meijers, *The Empirical Turn in the Philosophy of Technology* (Illustrated edition). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Tjiparuro, Z. (2025). Using design kits to test the problem-solving abilities of engineering students. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering Education*. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03064190241309043>
- Verbeek, P.-P. (2001). Don Ihde: The Technological Lifeworld. In A. W. M. Meijers, *The Empirical Turn in the Philosophy of Technology* (Illustrated edition). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Wiedemann, A., Wiesche, M., Gewalt, H., & Krcmar, H. (2023). Integrating development and operations teams: A control approach for DevOps. *Information and Organization*, 33(3). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoandorg.2023.100474>
- Wood, D. F. (2003). Problem based learning. *BMJ*, 326(7384), 328. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.326.7384.328>
- Zaccaria, V., Guziana, B., Senanayake, N., & Abeyweera, R. (2025). Challenge-Based Learning in Online Settings: Students' Perspective from the Energy for Circular Economy Master Program. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, 1280 LNNS, 117–128. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-83523-0_11
- Zhao, R. (2025). Enhancing student learning outcomes and career development through active engagement and support in STEM education. In *Student-Centered Learning: Enhancing Education Through Active Engagement* (pp. 23–44). Scopus.